

INTRODUCTION TO THE GAME OF VOLLEYBALL AND ITS STAGES.

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Annotation: The obtained results should serve as a basis for the application of teaching methods, stages and technology. The initial training process is carried out in several stages, and each of these stages includes its own methods and tools. General developmental exercises are used to improve the player's physical fitness and movement skills and skills necessary for the player. All exercises combined in accordance with their direction form the main parts of special training, including general physical, special physical, technical, tactical and game training. Each type of preparation has its own leading factors, with the help of which the desired goal is achieved.

Key words: training, technical training, initial training, preparation, game skills, training tools, special exercises, training methods, apparatus and equipment.

INTRODUCTION In addition to the development of physical education and mass sports, importance is being paid to the development of big sports in our country. Every year, international and world-class prestigious competitions are held in our republic, and the interest of young people in sports is increasing. Our athletes participate in Asian, World and Olympic competitions and achieve high results, glorifying the fame of our country. One of the ways to solve this problem is to reorient various types of targeted physical education programs to meet the needs of each student as fully as possible, to take into account the physical development and level of training of students as fully as possible. Unfortunately, although sports games, especially volleyball, are widely developed, high results are not being achieved in international competitions. Volleyball is included in the curriculum of

all educational institutions as a subject, and training and training processes are being held in sports clubs, children's and sports schools that operate outside of class and work. The process of preliminary teaching of sports skills is considered to be the foundation of the long-term sports training system . The more thorough and high-quality the preliminary training is from the organizational, methodological, scientific and material-technical point of view, the shorter and easier the training of sports substitutes will be. But this, of course, directly depends on the specialist's knowledge, professional skills and qualifications. Therefore, one of the most important and main sections of the training program for training specialists is the methodology (technology) of primary education. One of the main factors for achieving an effective result during the competition is the technical preparation and technical skill of the volleyball player . Therefore, the first and main goal of the teaching process is to master the technique of the game perfectly.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS Until now , a number of scientific studies have been carried out on the problems of theory and practice of physical education and sports in higher educational institutions, and the issues of the differentiated methodology of using sports games in the sports improvement groups of higher educational institutions have been highlighted. LRAirapetyans, MAGodik, 1991; Yu.D. Zheleznyak, 1994; MC Akhmatov , 2004 . Also VAKobzev, 1996; NAAanashkina, 1998; A. Zelensky, 1998; In scientific works of VPGuba, 2000 and others, the scientific-theoretical and practical bases and methods of using a differentiated approach in organizing the physical education process of young students were described. Movement and game skills - passing the ball, receiving (defense), putting the ball into play, hitting, blocking are mastered and improved in certain stages, using certain methods and tools. - will rise. This process is carried out on the basis of pedagogical, biopsychological and biomechanical laws.

RESULTS The teaching process is a pedagogical process that requires great skill and professional training from the trainer-teacher. But so if there is , the action (play qualification) performance reach to the technique to teach another important

reasons is also related. Including the child's activity, the number, quality, duration of training, auxiliary technical equipment, the conditions of the training place, the child's interest, wealth of movement, experience, etc. It should also be said that the period of mastering movement techniques depends on the child's family situation, his social and economic opportunities, and his mental state. The above-mentioned information and factors to be taken into account in the process of training should be included in planning documents based on a certain methodological procedure. In addition, it is necessary to identify the child's inner secret potential and existing factors with the help of selection programs and exercises. At the same time, all types of preparations are inextricably linked. For example, if the student is not well prepared physically, he will not be able to perform well the technical exercise of hitting in attack. In this case, training the student from the physical side is more useful than repeating the hitting method many times. The initial training should be carried out step by step and based on a full year of training. The first stage is to get acquainted with the studied movement technique. In this, telling, showing and explaining methods are used. Along with the coach's demonstration, visual aids such as film, visual film, scheme, field model, etc. are used. The demonstration should be accompanied by explanations. The first attempts of the coach-teacher form in them a primary sense of movement. The second stage is learning the technique in a simplified state. Success at this stage of learning in many cases depends on the correct selection of approach exercises. According to their structure, they should be close to the studied movement technique and should be able to be performed by students. Actions with a complex structure, that is, an attack blow, are divided into its main components. At this stage, management methods are used: commanding, giving instructions, seeing and hearing, observing, technical tools, etc. techniques such as hitting the ball, accuracy of landing, lighting or sound are of particular importance. The third stage is teaching technique in complicated conditions. The following are used in this: repetitive method, execution of movement in complex conditions, game and evaluation method, joint method, rotation exercises. Repetition

is key at this stage. Only repeated repetition builds proficiency. Repetition in order to develop skills requires performing exercises in different conditions, changing the conditions of movement, and gradually increasing the complexity. Exercises are performed even when tired, joint and game styles are aimed at simultaneously polishing the technique and solving the issues of developing special physical qualities and improving technical and tactical training and playing skills.

The fourth stage is to strengthen the movement during the game. In this, the method of interpretation of performed actions is used (pictures, tables, educational films, visual films), technical-tactical, special training tasks, game and competition methods are used during the game.

DISCUSSION In preparation and educational games, it is envisaged to study each method (skill), improve and perfect it. The best way to improve skills is to compete. The main means of training in volleyball, like other sports, is physical exercises. They are very different. Therefore, they are classified according to their role in solving the tasks at a certain stage of training . Such classification is based on the competitive activity of volleyball players. In this regard, exercises are divided into two large groups, these are the main or competition and auxiliary or training. In many cases, the effectiveness of tools for training volleyball movements directly depends on the methods of their use . Styles are selected and applied depending on the assigned task, level of training of the participants, specific conditions. Depending on the task, the same tool can be used in different ways. In addition, the sequence of tasks and types in each type of preparation has a certain logical connection. Tasks of one type of training change in quality and create a foundation for the next type of training. For example, preparatory exercises represent the general structure of the technical method being studied. Converging exercises serve as a bridge in the transition from special physical training to technical training . Technical exercises built on the basis of a certain level of complexity help to form tactical skills . On this basis, individual tactical actions will be studied later.

CONCLUSION The main movement in volleyball consists of walking, running, side-stepping, back-stepping, stepping-stopping, jumping. In many cases, movements are interpreted as not difficult, and they are ignored. This is a wrong idea. Because the player's choice of position and place to perform various actions has a direct impact on the effect of the performed action. Therefore, it is necessary to pay great attention to teaching movements.

The correct organization of the initial training process of the coach serves as the basis for the effective formation of such important tasks as ensuring the cohesion of the country's national teams and cultivating qualified sports reserves.

REFERENCES

1. Shermamatovich, M., Yalgashevich, K., & Narkulovich, S. (2021). The development of physical preparedness of student young people. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(1), 2699-2704.
2. Shermamatovich, M. M., Tursunovna, H. U., Zayniddinovich, N. I., Boltayevich, A. S., & Yalgashevich, K. S. (2021). Physical education of student youth in modern conditions. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(2), 1589-1593.
3. Shermamatovich, M. M. (2023). Psychological Description Of Sport And Psychological Development Of Sportsmen. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 17, 7-9.
4. Shermamatovich, M. M., Norkulovich, S. K., & Tursunovna, H. U. (2022). PLACE AND ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND VOLITIONAL TRAINING IN THE TRAINING PROCESS OF STUDENTS-BOXERS. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 8, 141-144.
5. Shermamatovich, M. M., & Boltaevich, A. (2022). INTERACTIVE LEARNING METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICAL CULTURE. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 7, 99-100.

6. Shermamatovich, M. M., & Boltaevich, A. (2022). INTERACTIVE LEARNING METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICAL CULTURE. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 7, 99-100.
7. Shermamatovich, M. M., Zayniddinovich, N. I., Boltaevich, A. S., Norqulovich, S. Q., Muzaffarovich, S. A., & Abriyevich, E. Q. Endurance Formation in General Physical Training Students. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(3), 356-359.
8. Yalgashevich, X. S., & Shermamatovich, M. M. Enhancing Athletes' Regained Performance Through Rational Nutrition. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, (1), 1-6.
9. Shermamatovich, M. M., & Latif, T. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 374-377.
10. Shermamatovich, M. M., & Aybxonovich, T. M. (2024). O'QUVCHILARNING FUTBOL BO'YICHA TEXNIK-TAKTIK TAYYORGARLIK TOMONLARINI O'RGANISH MUAMMOLARI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(1), 84-87.
11. Shermamatovich, M. M. (2023). THE SPORT OF WRESTLING AND THE LAWS OF THE FIELD OF WRESTLING. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(5), 84-88.
12. Shermamatovich, M. M. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF WRESTLING SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN AND AWAKENING OF THE CONCEPT OF PATRIOTISM IN STUDENTS. *JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING*, 2(5), 36-39.
13. Murodov Muzaffar Shermamatovich, Normaxmatov Ilxom Zayniddinovich, Axmedjanov Shuxrat Boltayivich, Ziyatov Muxammad Nomozovich, Sattarov Qarshiboy Norkulovich, & Khusainov Shamshidin Yalgashevich. (2024). PROPOSALS ON INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS OF ORGANIZING THE

ARCHITECTURE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL SPORTS FACILITIES. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 45(S2), 131–135. <https://doi.org/10.53555/jaz.v45iS2.3852>

14. [ERTALABKI BADAN TARBIYA HAMDA JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIKNING INSON ORGANIZMIGA FOYDASI](#) N.I.

Zayniddinovich – 2023

15. [FORENSIC ASSESSMENT OF THE NATURE OF DENTAL INJURIES](#)

OA Ergashevich, SE Islamov, NI Zainitdinovich - *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and ...*, 2022

16. [IMPROVING THE METHOD OF TRAINING BOXERS WITH THE APPLICATION OF PROTECTION" LEAVING TO THE SIDE"](#)

AS Boltaevich, NI Zayniddinovich

World Bulletin of Management and Law 8, 139-140, 2022

17. [ЗАЩИТА ПРАВ ПАЦИЕНТА ПРИ ПРОВЕДЕНИИ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТОВ](#)

ШЭ Исламов, КН Ураков, ИЗ Нормухматов - *Тверской Медицинский Журнал Учредители ...*

18. [PROPOSALS ON INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS OF ORGANIZING THE ARCHITECTURE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL SPORTS FACILITIES](#)

MMSNIZASBZMNSQNKS Yalgashevich *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 2 (45(S2)), 131–135., 2024

19. [МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ НАДПОЧЕЧНИКОВ ПРИ ВВЕДЕНИИ ДИСТИЛЛИРОВАННОЙ ВОДЫ](#)

Ш Исламов, Н Махматмурадова, И Нормухматов *Журнал гепато-гастроэнтерологических исследований* 2 (3.1), 22-28, 2021

20. [JISMONIY TARBIYA O'QITUVCHILARI FAOLIYATINING ILMIY – PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI](#) NI Zayniddinovich *Journal Of New Century*

Innovations 4 (No. 1 (2024):), 133-135, 2024

21. [АСПЕКТЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ КОМАНДНЫХ СПОРТОВ И СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ](#)

https://academicsresearch.ru/public/journals/17/cover_issue_133_en_US.jpg 2 ..., 2024

22. [IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASS CHILDREN](#) NI Zainiddinovich International Journal of Formal 3 (3), 66–69., 2024

23. [THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ROLE OF SPORTS AND GAMES IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION](#) NI Zayniddinovich Genius Journals Publishing Group, 17 (ISSN: 2795-7365), 10-12, 2023

24. [THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ROLE OF SPORTS AND GAMES IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION](#) NI Zayniddinovich <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb>, Genius Journals Publishing Group, 17 (ISSN: 2795-7365), 10-12, 2023

25. [Basic Football Elements Terms and Conditions and Cluster-Based Training of Tasks](#) NI Zayniddinovich Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences 2 (Issue –11), 106-108, 2023

26. [The Role Of Physical Culture In The Life Of Students](#) Normaxmatov Ilxom Zayniddinovich international journal of scientific & technology research volume 10 (issn ..., 2021

27. Хусайинов Ш. Я. и др. ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА КОМАНДНЫХ ВИДОВ СПОРТА ДЛЯ АДАПТАЦИОННЫХ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2024. – Т. 6. – №. 1. – С. 47-55.

28. Shermamatovich M. M., Yalgashevich X. S., Muzaffar o'g'li S. A. SPORT KURASHIDA SARALASH: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2024. – Т. 6. – №. 1. – С. 69-75.

29. Shermamatovich M. M. The Role of Physical Education in Our Life //International Journal of Formal Education. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 63-65.

30. Муратов М. Ш., ўғли Шермаматов А. М. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОМУ ВОСПИТАНИЮ //Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-192.

31. Shermatovich M. M. JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT DARSLARIDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING JIHATLARI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2024. – Т. 48. – №. 1. – С. 130-132.

32. Shermamatovich M. M. et al. Proposals On Innovative Solutions Of Organizing The Architecture Of Multifunctional Sports Facilities //Journal of Advanced Zoology. – 2024. – Т. 45.

33. Shermamatovich M. M., Aybxonovich T. M. O'QUVCHILARNING FUTBOL BO'YICHA TEXNIK-TAKTIK TAYYORGARLIK TOMONLARINI O'RGANISH MUAMMOLARI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2024. – Т. 44. – №. 1. – С. 84-87.